

AN ASSESSMENT OF SERIALS MANAGEMENT IN KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION LIBRARY, ILORIN.

By

ABUBAKAR HAJARAT (MRS)

*Kwara State College
of Education, Ilorin, Library.*

Abstract

The study aimed to find out the assessment of serials management at Kwara State College of Education Ilorin, library. The researcher used descriptive research designed to carry out the research with the aid of self-design questionnaire to obtain the relevant information from the respondents who are senior library staff of College of Education, Ilorin library. The collected data were analyzed by making use of simple percentage analysis. The findings revealed that there is no library written policy on type of serials materials to be acquired, and who should do the selection and quantity to be acquired. Also findings revealed that, the college serials collections were properly organized for easy accessibility of the users thus, the researcher recommended that the library should have library written policy and also provided repository for preservation and conservation of the library collection.

Introduction

Serials materials are part of library resources that are acquired, processed, preserved, and disseminated to the users in order to develop the habit of self-learning on the use of serials collection that may contribute intellectual development and also Serials materials introduce the user to the difference types of serials collection as supplementary materials for their recreation and research purposes Serials materials as the names implies are the publication that come out frequently, either daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly, annually, bi-annually and they usually come with volume or issue Number also come out in successive part with most current information such materials include annual reports, magazines, journals, conference proceeding,

micro-graphic series which are needed for latest information etc. A professional in charge of serial publications is called the serial librarian and these publications could either come in print or in non-print. Ogbomo (2000) defines serials as “a publication issues in successive part usually at regular intervals end as a rule, intended to be continued indefinitely”. Okiy (2008) says, serials constituted important. part of the resources of an academic library because they provide the latest information on research and current affairs. For this, it is necessary for the serials division to be as complete in its holding in order to support the teaching, learning, recreation and research programmes of the college. The serials Collection are. The serials Collection are both current and back-sets of periodicals for lecturers and students for easy access to information within. the library.

Lawal (1982) described serials as the nerve centre of any academic library because they contain the most up-to date information. According to Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules (1978) serials are publications in any medium issued -in successive parts bearing in. numerical or chronological designatories and intended to be continued. indefinitely.

Elaturoti et al (1990) said that, because serials contain more current information than those in monographs they form. an impart component of the library collection. Aboyade (1979) stressed that one would have to look in the appropriate journals for the latest and up-to-date opinions and development with subject disciplines. Osbon (1980) said that aerials as a printed work appearing regularly of unlimited duration and pays attention only to the development in a special field. Adedeji (1984) in his own view said that the term serials is used interchangeably in everyday conversation to mean magazines, journals or any publication of that nature while Adio (2006) opines that serials are essential tool of teaching and research in academic endeavour and remain a potent tool for dissemination of knowledge. Amaakaven (1995) defined serials management as formulations of routines and procedures for administering serials collection. These routines include such function as selection and acquisition, disseminations, weeding, filling gaps in backrooms, treatment of unbound issues, preparation for binding and policy for binding back issue.

Friend (2000) observed that, the basic serials management activities Include analysis of user needs, inter- and- intra-library communication, policy development, budgeting and allocation of resources., contract negotiations, macro-evaluations of collection, macro-evaluation for selection, relegation, preservation or Withdrawal of

stock and system evaluation.

Better and Wade (2001) said that, serials management (print and e-journal) in the learning centres of Sheffield Hallam University examined traditional Areas of serials management namely, budget management, selection criteria, Bibliographic information and general collection management.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

The main objective of the study is to assess how the serials collections are being managed in an academic library (Kwara State College of Education, Library).

THE SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES ARE

Find out:-

- a. How they acquire and organize serials materials in the library
- b. Assess the modes of preserving and conserving the serials materials in the library
- c. Evaluate the level of usage of serials materials in the library.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- a. What is the College Library policy statement on the acquisition of serial materials?
- b. How does the college library process its serials collections before making it available to the users?
- c. Which type of preservation method do they apply in preserving and conserving your collections?
- d. How are serials materials being organized?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will bring about the awareness on how to assess, manage, conserve and preserve the serial materials in the library.

It will also serve as a guideline for improvement on the acquisition of serials materials in the library through the introduction of library written policy which will enhance better selection and acquisition of serial materials. It will assist the college librarian to know where and how to acquire more serials materials in the college library and also aid the college serials librarian on how to select and acquire recent serials materials.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used a questionnaire which was administered on 15 staff of the college of Kwara State Education Ilorin, library i.e. those on librarian cadre and officers cadre all of them have worked in college library serials unit. Thus, the questionnaire was given to them mid collected after two days

Research

Question 1:- What are the college library policy statements on the acquisition of serials materials?

Table 1: - Responses of the respondents on the policy statement as regards acquisition of serials materials

S/N	Questionnaire items	Yes	%	No	%	Total
1	Does your library have a policy statement on acquisition of serial materials?	04	26.7%	11	73.3%	15
2	Is it stated in the policy who should do the selection of serial materials?	04	26.7%	11	73.3%	15
3	Is it stated in the policy the number of serial materials to be acquired?	04	26.7%	11	73.3%	15

The result gathered from table 1 shows that 4 (26.7%) of the respondents agreed that the college of education Ilorin., library has policy statement on acquisition of their serial material. while, 11 (73.3%) disagreed on the issue raised by the researcher. This implies that no written policy statement on acquisition of serial materials.

Item 2 of the same table vividly shows that the policy has not stated who do the selection of serial. materials with 4 (26.7%) of the respondents agreed on the question while 11 (73.3%) of the respondents disagreed with the questions raised

In item 3:- 40% of the respondents agreed that it is stated in the policy number of serials materials to be acquired while 60% disagreed on the issue.

Research Question 2:- How does the College Library process its serials collection before making it available to the users?

Table 2:- Summary of the respondents on, the process of the serials collection before making sit available to the users.

S/N	Questionnaire items	Yes	%	No	%	Total
1	Do you catalogue your serial collections?	2	13.3%	13	86.7%	15
2	Do you process the serial materials through kardex?	14	93.3%	1	6.7%	15
3	Do you stamp your materials before accessioning?	15	100%	0	100%	15
4	Do you have separate ledger for accessioning the serial materials?	15	100%	0	100%	15

Looking at the result of table .2, it case be seen that. 2 (13.3%) of the respondents agreed that the serials collections are being catalogued white 86.7% of the respondents disagreed.

In items 2 of the same table shows that 14(93.3%) of the respondents agreed that the serials materials are being processed through kardex. While the remaining 1 (6.7%)of the respondents disagreed on the questions

In items 3 and 4 of the same: table it is shown that all the respondents agreed on the issues raised by the researcher which signify serial;; materials were being

stamped and accessioned in separate ledger before making it available to the users.

Research Question 3: - Which type of preservations method do you apply in preserving and conserving the serials collections?

S/N	Questionnaire items	Yes	%	No	%	Total
1	Do your library have conservation and preservation policy for their serials materials?	13	86.7%	2	13.3%	15
2	Do your library keep their seminal, conference paper, annual reports etc. pamphlet boxes?	15	100%	0	0%	15
3	Do you have conservation and preservation repository?	1	6.7%	14	93.3%	15
4	Which method do you prefer most in preserving serials materials?					
		Yes	%	No	%	Total
a.	Tidying and Cleaning	2	13.4%	0	0%	2
b.	Fumigating	0	0%	0	0%	0
c.	All of the above	13	86.6%	0	0%	13
	Total					15

The table above shows that 86.7% of the respondents says that, the studied library has conservation and preservation policy for their serial materials while 26.7% of the respondents says that, no policy stated for conservation method.

In items 2 shows that 100% of the respondents agreed that their seminal, conference papers, annual reports are being kept inside the boxes while none of the respondents disagreed with the questions.

In items 3 of the same table 93.3% of the respondents claimed that college library don't have conservation- and preservation laboratory while, the remaining 6.6% of the respondents claimed they have.

In item 4 of the same table on the issue of most method prefer in preserving serials materials, 86.0% of the respondents prefer all the method raised by the researcher such as tidying up of serials collection, cleaning method, and fumigating while the remaining 13.4% mostly prefer tidying up and cleaning method respectively.

Research Question 4: - How are the serials materials being organized?

Table 4:- Summary of the respondents' opinion on how the library organize its serials materials.

S/N	Questionnaire items	Yes	%	No	%	Total
1	Does your library organize their serials materials?	15	100%	0	0%	15
2	Do you have magazine rack for holding magazine?	15	100%	0	0%	15
3	Do you provide space for back-issue of the news papers?	15	100%	0	0%	15
4	Are journals and other serials collections being organized for easy accessibility of the users?	15	100%	0	0%	15

Answers to the four questions in the questionnaire items above. It was discovered that, 100% of the staff that answered the questions in the college library agreed on the (4) items raised by the researcher. This implies that there are adequate organization of serial collection in the College Library which pave way for the easy accessibility of the users. Thus, the serials materials in the College Library are organized through magazine rack and Journals are arranged according; to their subject: based and processed card are filed in the kardex boxes for easy accessibility of the users.

DISCUSSION

The findings on the issue of whether the college library has acquisition policy on serials materials show that the library has no stated policy on acquisition of serials materials and also no policy on who should do (he selection and it has not stated the number of copies to be acquired. This is contrary to Akobi (2004) Akobi observed that without an explicit: policy statement, there will be inconsistency and in balance selection of serial materials. Akobi said further that where the serials policy is lacking, the staff who select the materials dwell on their discretion which is not too good for a balanced and well planned serials collections for high quality teaching and research.

In addition to the findings its shows that serials collections are being processed through the accessioning and file cards in kardex boxes.

Preservation sand conservation, the college library adopted the cleaning, tidying-up and fumigation method in order to sustain the durability of the serial materials as posited by Adio (2006-) who said that library preserved and protected its serials publication against being damaged and lost by binding restricted access, photocopying, microfilming and exit control.

The periodicals in the college library are well organized by providing for back issues of the newspapers, magazines, journals, seminar papers, conference papers workshop papers and other ephemerals are put in boxes this finding is in support of Dina (2002) who said that, the materials acquired should be processed and organized in a specific way to facilitate appropriate storage, easy retrieval and free access to the users and also the leveel of usage of this serial,, materials in the college library were, moderate.

CONCLUSION

In view of the findings, it can be concluded that, college of education Ilorin, library has not adopted the acquisition. on selection and acquisition of serials materials nor written policy the number of serials materials to be acquired and who should do the selection. The study also showed that, there is adequate oranzation of serials materials such as journals, magazines, newspapers, etc. for easy accessibility of the users. Finally, the preservation method is in practice for durability of the collections.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For effective and efficient practice, the writer recommends as follows.

The library must have well stated policy for the acquisition and selection of serials materials so that the library will be able to select and acquire recent materials also such policy must be reviewed and updated from time to time. Finally, there should be repository for preservation and conservation of all library collections.

Abstract

The effectiveness of modern information retrieval mechanism in library administrations. African Journal of Education and Technology, Vol. 18 No. 1, 2007. Maimasa is one of the outstanding scholars of the contemporary world who left indelible impression in Ilorin Emirate and neighboring towns in Nigeria on the subject of Islamic Sufism. The present study is an attempt to assess his intellectual problems and prospects. Nigerian Librarian, Vol. 18 No. 2, 1976. It was discovered after the study that the scholar was a multifaceted personality. Olay, R. I. (2008). Library guide: Delta State University Library, Akoka, Warri. A prolific Arabic writer, who made a huge contribution to the development of Arabic language and Sufism. It was also discovered that he was a Qadriyyan Sufi order but he does not discriminate among the two orders. In: The Journal of Information Studies, Vol. 2, No. 2, 2007. Thomas, A. (2007). Serial management in polytechnic libraries in Nigeria. Suggested to Nigerian Serials and Librarians to pay more attention on the works of West African Muslim Scholars in the field of Qur'anic exegesis, Sufism, poetry etc.

1.0 Introduction

The virtue of knowledge acquisition in Islam cannot be overemphasized. More than any other religion of the world, Islam places high premium on seeking for knowledge. According to Malik (2000), the

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